

SIP23: Programs to simulate input data for Step 2/3
by S. Söderhjelm

1. Introduction

The output from the Step 1 processing of a set consists of a single quantity, the abscissa (together with its estimated mean error), for each star observed in that set. For the development and testing of Step 2/3 software, a sizeable number of observations are required, and we describe here a simple simulation program to create such observations.

In principle, we create first a reasonably realistic star-catalogue giving simulated astrometric parameters for some 10^4 stars. For given set-intervals and RGC-poles, the stars observed in each set are singled out and their coordinate abscissae determined. (The satellite motion is neglected and pure geocentric positions used). Assuming reasonable observational errors, simulated observations are derived for each set at a time.

2. The star-catalogue

This may contain an arbitrary number of stars, but mostly some 10-20000 are used. The positions (α, δ) at a chosen mean epoch are always random over the sphere. The other parameters are derived from simple statistical distribution laws.

As for the magnitudes, the present simulation gives only stars brighter than $m_H (\equiv (B+V)/2) = 9$. In this range, the input-catalogue is expected to be nearly complete, and the accumulated number of stars over the sphere can be taken as

$$\lg N(m_H) = \text{const.} + 0.59 m_H - 0.01 m_H^2 \quad (1)$$

This relation was derived from Söderhjelm's recent statistical model for binaries (see below), but it also fits the data in Astrophysical Quantities (Allen, 1973). The number of simulated stars is lower than the real number of bright stars, and eq. (1) is used only to give a realistic relative distribution over magnitude. In practice, to simulate a magnitude, one takes

$$m = 29.5 - (420.25 - 100 \lg x)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

with x a pseudo-random number in the interval $]0,1[$.

A star with a thus simulated apparent magnitude must now be placed at a certain distance. A simple but useful approximation is to assume that (due to the combined effect of a luminosity function decreasing with luminosity and an increasing effective volume) the absolute magnitudes (for given m) are normally distributed. From the assumptions used in a statistical model for binaries (Söderhjelm, 1984, International Conference on Astrometric Binaries, Bamberg), one obtains the following parameters for such normal distributions

$$\begin{aligned} \langle M \rangle &= -1.62 + 0.37 m \\ \sigma_M &= 2.15 - 0.02 m \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In order to get the distance from the distance modulus y ($\equiv m - M$), we also have to correct for absorption, and the approximation formula used is

$$r = 10^{(1+0.2 y)} [1 - 0.0037(y-1.3)^2] \quad (4)$$

Given m from (2), we get a random M using (3) and the distance (parallax) then follows by (4).

It remains to specify the radial velocity and proper motions. Again we simplify and assume a kinematical model with a constant solar motion 20 km/s towards the apex $\alpha = 18^\circ$, $\delta = 30^\circ$, plus an isotropic gaussian velocity distribution with $\sigma = 20$ km/s. Given thus the space-velocity vector $\underline{v}$ and the position vector $\underline{u}$ for a star, we find the velocity components v_α , v_δ and v_r through

$$\begin{aligned} v_r &= \underline{u} \cdot \underline{v} \\ \underline{v}_T &= \underline{v} - v_r \underline{u} \\ v_\delta &= v_T(3)/\cos \delta \\ v_\alpha &= -v_T(1) \sin \alpha + v_T(2) \cos \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and μ_α , μ_δ then follow from the distance.

2. The scanning-law

The satellite is assumed to scan the sky according to the nominal scanning-law (Lindegren 84-04-17)

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= 43^\circ \\ \bar{v} &= 6.4 \lambda_s \\ v &= \bar{v} - 0.16378 \cos \bar{v} - 0.01308 \sin 2\bar{v} + 0.00123 \cos 3\bar{v} + \\ &\quad + 0.00012 \sin 4\bar{v} \\ (\Omega &= \Omega_0 + \dot{\Omega}t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where λ_s is the nominal solar longitude

$$\lambda_s = L + 2e \sin g + 1.25 e^2 \sin 2g$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} L &= -1.38691 + 0.0172021240 d \\ g &= -0.04114 + 0.0172019696 d \\ e &= 0.016714 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and where the time d is counted in days from J 1988.0.

Ideally, to determine which stars are observed, the axial scanning motion (Ω) should be followed in detail (with a time-step equal to the 19.2 sec crossing-time over the FOV). This is quite out of the question, however, because at each of these millions of times we would have to scan at least part of the star-catalogue to look for observed stars. Instead, we use the smoothness of the scanning motion to make a good estimate. For the reference times t_1 (near the beginning) and t_2 (near the end of a set), we calculate the scan axes $\underline{z}_1$ and $\underline{z}_2$ which are then compared with the position vector $\underline{u}$ of

each star in the catalogue. The star is considered as observed when the criteria (Lindegren 1981-02-06)

$$\text{Max} [(z_1 \cdot u), (z_2 \cdot u)] > -\sin (w/2)$$

and

(8)

$$\text{Min} [(z_1 \cdot u), (z_2 \cdot u)] < \sin (w/2)$$

are both fulfilled, ($w = 0.9$ is the width of the FOV). The stars in the "main body" of the set are then correctly included, but some that are scanned only near the beginning or end may be missed or falsely included. (This is of little significance, however, because the scanning-law is only nominal, and the "real" scanning might give still another selection of stars.) In the present simulations, t_1 and t_2 are taken 1 hour from the set limits (close to 1/2 scan). The sets are given randomly variable lengths (uniformly distributed between 10^h and 14^h), and the scan-poles at set mid-points are chosen as the RGC-poles. The first set starts at J 1988.0 + 10^7 sec, and 2000 sets are normally simulated.

3. The simulated observations

For an "observed" star, we first calculate its coordinate direction at the set mid-time, using Lindegren's (1984-07-27) codirs-subroutine. This takes into account the proper motion since the star-catalogue epoch (J 1988.0 + $5 \cdot 10^7$ s) and the parallax with respect to the barycentre. A geocentric observer is assumed, and the earth's barycentric position is calculated by Lindegren's (1984-06-08) earth-routine (based on formulae by Chapront, Francou and Morando, Bureau des Longitudes, 1984).

With the components of the coordinate direction $uco(1:3)$ and the RGC pole $z(1:3)$, we may now calculate the coordinate abscissa v from

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \rho \cos \delta_r \cos v &= z(1) uco(2) - uco(1) z(2) \\ \cos \rho \cos \delta_r \sin v &= z(1) [z(1) uco(3) - uco(1) z(3)] \\ &\quad + z(2) [z(2) uco(3) - uco(2) z(3)] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where ρ is the ordinate and $\delta_r = \sin^{-1}(z(3))$.

To this abscissa-value is then added a gaussian "observational error" with a standard deviation $\epsilon(\text{mas})$ given by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= 3.4 & m &\leq 6 \\ \epsilon &= 1.0 + 0.4 m & 6 < m &\leq 9 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

see Lindegren (NDAC LO/017, 1983-02-07). Each set is also given a "zero-point error" taken from a normal distribution with $\sigma = 50$ mas.

4. Program details

In practice, two separate programs are used. The first (SIP23A) generates the star catalogue, set-intervals and RGC-poles, and stores them in unformatted Fortran-files. The second program (SIP23B) reads these files and makes the real calculations. With (the practical maximum) 20000 stars, each

set includes some 360 observations, and these are generated in about 20 seconds on the HP9000 (some 12 hours for 2000 sets).

The original star-catalogue gives the true astrometric parameters as used for simulating the observations. A "degraded" version is also generated, to be used as input-catalogue in the Step 2/3-solution. All parallaxes and radial velocities are here set to zero, and the positions and proper motions have gaussian dispersions of 1" and 0".03/y respectively (in each coordinate). The input magnitudes also differ from the true ones by a gaussian $\sigma = 0.1$. A similar "input-catalogue" for the RGC poles has 0".05 errors in the coordinates.

The data generated by the program shall finally be output to the user. In order to make this output reasonably transferable even in binary format, it is given as non-negative integers only. The integer-files are output in fix-length (2000 integer*4) records on 1600 bpi magnetic tape. The five files on a tape are then:

I. TRUE STAR CATALOGUE

Each 2000-integer record contains data for 200 stars. The interpretation of the integers for each star is as follows:

I(1) = star number
 I(2) (magnitude); $m = (I(2) - 10000) / 100$
 I(3), I(4) (R.A.); $\alpha = I(3) 2^{-24} + I(4) 2^{-48}$ (rad, interval]0, 2 π [)
 I(5), I(6) (decl.); $\delta = I(5) 2^{-24} + I(6) 2^{-48}$ (rad, interval]0, 2 π [)
 I(7) (p.m. in R.A.); $\mu_{\alpha} \cos \delta = (I(7) - 10^8) 10^{-19}$ (rad/s)
 I(8) (p.m. in decl.); $\mu_{\delta} = (I(8) - 10^8) 10^{-19}$ (rad/s)
 I(9) (parallax); $\pi = I(9) 10^{-12}$ (rad)
 I(10) (radial velocity); $RV = I(10) - 10^6$ (m/s)

II. INPUT STAR CATALOGUE

Format exactly as file I, but approximate stellar data.

III. TRUE RGC CATALOGUE

Each record contains data for 250 sets in its first 1750 integers, (the last 250 integers are zeros). The interpretation of the 7 integers for each set is as follows:

I(1) = set number
 I(2) = set mid-time (seconds after J 1988.0)
 I(3), I(4) (R.A. of RGC pole); $= I(3) 2^{-24} + I(4) 2^{-48}$ (rad,]0, 2 π [)
 I(5), I(6) (decl. of RGC pole); $= I(5) 2^{-24} + I(6) 2^{-48}$ (rad,]0, 2 π [)
 I(7) (set zero-point); $= (I(7) - 10^7) 10^{-11}$ (rad)

IV. INPUT RGC CATALOGUE

Format as file III, approximate RGC-positions and zero set zero-points.

V. ABSCISSA CATALOGUE

The main output-file has the data for one set in one 2000-integer record, (the non-used portion filled with zeros). The successive integers are:

I(1) = set number

I(2) = no (number of stars observed in the set)

- for k = 1 to no - - - - -

I(4k-1) = star number

I(4k), I(4k+1) ("obs" abscissa); $v = I(4k) 2^{-24} + I(4k+1) 2^{-48}$ (rad,]0, 2 π [)

I(4k+2) (std. dev. of abscissa); $\epsilon = I(4k+2) 2^{-32}$ (rad)

- - - - -

For the standard case with 20000 stars and 2000 sets, we will have 100 records in files I and II, 8 records in files III and IV, and 2000 records in file V, 17.73 Mb in all.